

Evaluation and Participatory Variety Selection of Common Bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) Varieties in Dawro Zone, South Western Region of Ethiopia

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Abstract

Farmers in the study area exhibit a unique tendency to choose varieties based on selection criteria rather than tested yields in the district. To ensure farmer participation, a study was conducted on six farmers' farms, utilizing farmers as replicas in a Randomized Complete Block Design. Ten common bean crop varieties underwent evaluation on these farms to assess varieties in terms of farmer participation and identify priority criteria during the 2019 and 2020 production years. Plot sizes were standardized to 4m plot lengths with inter and intra-spacing of 40cm and 10cm, respectively. The seed and NPSB fertilizer rate were set at 100kg/ha and 122kg/ha, respectively. Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) were observed among treatments for plant height, days to 50% flowering, days to 90% maturity, and yield over two years. Notably, the common bean varieties Remeda, DAB 96, and SER 119 yielded 1641, 1601, and 1588.7kg/ha, respectively. Additionally, the farmers in the district preferred red-seeded varieties for production and consumption due to superior seed per pod, pod per plant, seed size, seed color, and seed yield. Moreover, these farmers preferred varieties established tolerance to major common bean diseases which were common in the district. Consequently, these high-yielding, farmers preferred, and disease-tolerant varieties are recommended for demonstration and large-scale production in the study regions and agro-ecological zones similar to those the trial was implemented in south western region of Ethiopia.

Keywords: *common bean, evaluate, selection, performance, participation.*

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Introduction

The common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L, $2n=22$) is a self-pollinating diploid legume crop belonging to the Fabaceae family. Presently, the common bean contributes to crop diversification, soil fertility maintenance, and protein sources in global agricultural and food systems (Beebe, 2014). In Ethiopia, this crop holds significant importance as the second most crucial staple food crop, following only maize, and is cultivated by more than 3 million households (Katungi et al., 2010).

Common beans are among Ethiopia's most valuable legume crops, serving as a crucial source of cash, food, and exports (Asfaw et al., 2009). Ethiopia has cultivated common beans on 306,186.59 hectares of

land, yielding 520,979.327tons (CSA, 2018), substantial coverage and output in the southern region of the country.

Participatory variety selection trials focusing on red-colored common bean varieties in different parts of Ethiopia have also revealed significant varietal responses and differences in preference. In western Ethiopia, the performance of 15 common bean genotypes tested in acidic soils showed variations (Habtamu et al., 2019).

Farmers in the Dawro zone have recognized the common bean as both a production and a consumption crop. However, there has been limited research on the performance evaluation of improved common bean varieties with active farmer participation. Consequently, the trial aimed to assess the performance of newly released common bean varieties, involving farmers in the process, and to ascertain the crop preferences of the farmers.

Materials and Methods

Study Area Description

The research was conducted in the Dawro zone, situated approximately 500km southwest of Ethiopia's capital, Addis Ababa, and 319km southwest of Hawassa, the seat of the Sidama region. The geographical coordinates of the zone range between latitudes, 5°34'1631"N and 7°20'57"N, and longitudes 36°22'13"E and 37°51'25" E. The elevation in the area varies from 500 to 3600 meters. The temperature ranges between 16°C to 24°C, and the average humidity is approximately 56%. Leptosols are the predominant soil type, constituting 91.1 percent of the total. The weather, including temperature and rainfall, at the test site is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Mean Rainfall and Temperature of Dawro Zone, Southern Ethiopia

Treatments and Experimental Design

From 2019 to 2020, ten released common bean varieties were tested in six farmers' fields utilizing a randomized complete block design. The experimental treatments comprised ten red-colored common

bean varieties characterized by varying seed sizes, and the design included maintaining a central location (Table 1). Farmers were presented with additional alternatives, incorporating recently released varieties for comparison with the local varieties they already possessed. This approach aimed to minimize the risk of adoption failure, providing farmers with the opportunity to assess and compare new varieties with their existing ones. Moreover, it facilitated the integration of farmers' desired traits into the breeding program.

The common bean varieties were planted in six rows, each measuring four meters, with a 40-cm inter-row spacing and 10-cm intra-row spacing, utilizing a seed rate of 100kg ha⁻¹. The harvested area amounted to 6.4m², divided into four rows of 4m each. Weed control was maintained through regular hand-weeding throughout the experiment. NPSB (18.9N, 37.7 P2O5, 6.95S, and 0.1B) fertilizer was applied at a rate of 122 kg ha⁻¹, and other agronomic techniques were implemented based on the recommendations specific to each site. The detailed description of the common bean varieties employed in the experiment is presented in tabular form below (Table 1).

Table 1. Descriptions of Common Bean Varieties Used for the Experiment, 2019-2020, in the Dawro Zone

S.N	Variety Name	Year of release	Size	Seed color	Maintaining /breeding center
1.	Hawassa Dume (SNNPR-120)	2008	Small	Red	Hawassa ARC
2.	SER 119	2014	Small	Red	Melkassa ARC
3.	F10 B.sel new Bilfa 58 (kello)	2017	Large	Red	Melkassa ARC
4.	SCR 26 (Sekia/RORI)	2017	Small	Red	Hawassa ARC
5.	Tatu (ETAW-01-L-7-6K)	2014	Large	Speckled	Hawassa ARC
6.	DAB 96 (Zo asho)	2017	Large	Red	Melkassa ARC
7.	SCR 15(Keyyo)	2019	Small	Red	Melkassa ARC
8.	Nasir (Dicta-105)	2003	Small	Red	Melkassa ARC
9.	Remeda (AFR-702-1)	2014	Large	Red	Hawassa ARC
10.	SER 125	2014	Small	Red	Melkassa ARC

Note: - YR= year of release, ARC = Agricultural Research Center

Data Collection and Statistical Analysis

Data on plant height (cm), phenological aspects (days to 50% flowering, days to 90% maturity), seed per pod, pod per pod, and grain yield in kg ha⁻¹ were collected and analyzed using SAS 9.2 version (SAS, 2009). Twenty farmers, comprising 14 men and 6 women, identified seven criteria for assessing common bean varieties to determine their preferences. These criteria included ground cover, number of seeds per pod, pods per plant, seed size, seed color, pod loading, and grain yield. Visual evaluations of the varieties were conducted during the flowering and maturity stages. Attributes were rated on a scale from 1 to 5, with 5 indicating not preferred, 4 as less preferred, 3 as somewhat desired, 2 as strongly preferred, and 1 as excellent. Farmers were provided with five seeds and instructed to place them in a container based on the qualities and varieties mentioned above. The total count for each trait per variety was calculated by counting seeds, and the variety with the lowest total count received the top rank/place.

Results and Discussion

Combined ANOVA of Common Bean Varieties

There was a significant difference ($P < 0.001$) among common bean varieties tested for two years in the analysis of grain yield, days to 50% flowering, days to 90% maturity, pod per plant, and plant height traits (Table 2).

The tested common bean varieties exhibited a significant difference in yield and yield-related traits. This substantial yield variation among different legume crop varieties aligns with findings reported by various authors, supporting the current results. Notably, significant differences in yield have been observed in common bean (Fekadu, 2013; Habtamu et al., 2019; Demelash et al., 2019) and chickpea (Habtamu et al., 2019) by other researchers. Similarly, a combined analysis of variance revealed significant differences in mean squares for days to 50% flowering, days to 90% maturity, and plant height, consistent with results reported by Legesse et al. (2015) and Asrat and Mathew (2014) in their studies on the variation of these traits in common bean and chickpea crop varieties, respectively.

Table 2. Mean Square for Seed Yield (kg ha⁻¹) and Yield Related Traits of Common Bean Varieties from Combined ANOVA, 2019-2020 Cropping Seasons in the Dawro Zone

SV	Loc	rep (loc)	Trt	Loc*Trt	Error	Mean	SD
DF	3	8	9	27	73		
Yield	817504.8	13942.3	20266.8*	61886.15		1321.46	98.37
DTF	617.9	6.07	7.96*	4.799	3.326	45.13	1.45
DTM	37.66	14.59	126.79*	65.81	7.92	91.96	3.64
PH	244.35	13.96	278.75*	272.43	47.99	64.73	12.98
SDPPD	8.68	7.75	2.96	2.11	2.71	4.82	1.02
PDPPT	95.45	127.4	127.4*	46.4	36.14	18.22	1.04

Note: *SV= source of variation, DF=degree of freedom, DTF= days to flowering, DTM= days to maturity, PH= plant height, SDPPD = seed per pod, PDPPT= pod per plant, Loc = location, rep = replication, trt = treatment, SD = standard deviation (measure of variation of a set of data in terms of the amounts by which the values deviate from their mean)

The Mean Values for Yield and Related Traits

The mean of yield and related traits of common bean varieties tested in Dawro zone is displayed below in the Table 3.

The mean values of yield traits of the common bean varieties were analyzed, revealing an average yield of 1321.46 kg per hectare. Notably, varieties such as Remeda, DAB 96, and SER 119 exhibited impressive yields of 1641, 1601, and 1588.7 kg per hectare, respectively. Simon et al. (2020) also reported higher yields for Remeda and SER 119 compared to 33 other common bean genotypes in a study conducted in southern parts of Ethiopia. These varieties are likely suitable for farming in agro-ecological zones similar to those indicated in Table 3. The tested common bean varieties exhibited significant differences in yield and related parameters, including days to 50% flowering, days to 90% maturity, plant height, number of seeds per pod, grain yield, and pods per plant. The mean values for days to 50% flowering, days to 90% maturity, plant height (cm), and yield (kg per hectare) were analyzed and found to be 40.87, 92.19, 63.18, and 1297.8, respectively, for the common bean varieties. Team et al. (2017) noted variations in the number of days to maturity among common bean varieties. Similar findings have been reported regarding the variation of these traits in common bean by studies such as Habtamu et al. (2019), Mekonen et al. (2010) and Kwabena et al. (2016).

Table 3. The Mean of Yield and Related Traits of Common Bean Varieties from the 2019-2020 Cropping Seasons in the Dawro Zone

No	Varieties	DTF	DTM	PH	Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)
1	Hawassa Dume (SNNPR-120)	39.42	89.50	59.42	1476.7
2	SER 119	40.08	90.83	60.00	1588.7
3	F10 B.sel new Bilfa 58 (kello)	40.08	93.33	66.08	1406.0
4	SCR 26 (Sekia/RORI)	40.67	90.25	56.00	1242.3
5	Tatu (ETAW-01-L-7-6K)	41.08	91.67	71.33	1549.3
6	DAB 96 (Zo asho)	41.67	98.67	63.75	1601.3
7	SCR 15 (Keyyo)	41.38	89.62	64.31	1432.0
8	Nasir (Dicta-105)	40.75	91.25	61.83	1286.3
9	Remeda (AFR-702-1)	40.83	97.08	67.75	1641.0
10	SER 125	40.67	89.92	61.25	1281.3
	Mean	40.87*	92.19*	63.18*	1321.46*
	LSD	3.69	3.89	7.97	176.53
	CV	11.19	5.24	15.64	16.56

Note: DTF= days to 50% flowering, DTM= Days to 90% maturity, PH= plant height, kg ha⁻¹= kilogram per hectare

Farmers' Evaluation of Common Bean Varieties

The evaluation of the common bean varieties took into accounts both researchers' data and the criteria preferred by district farmers. The traits of common bean crop varieties used by the district farmers for evaluation, along with the ranked varieties, are presented in Table 4 below.

In a participatory variety selection of ten common bean varieties, farmers' preference criteria revealed variations among the varieties. Among all tested varieties, Remeda, DAB 96, and SER 119 occupied the first, second, and third ranks. The popularity of these varieties, red-colored common bean varieties, was attributed to their marketability. They were particularly preferred in the preparation of 'Nefro' (boiled common bean grain mixed with maize), providing a red color to maize when cooked together. In the study district, farmers' choices for SER 119 and Remeda varieties surpassed other tested varieties, reflecting their importance for both home consumption and the local market. In Ethiopia, red-colored common beans are predominantly cultivated for the domestic market and export, while white common beans are mainly grown for export (Ferris and Kaganzi, 2008; Berhanu et al., 2018).

Table 4. Matrix of Ranking of Common Bean Varieties Across Two Seasons (2019-2020) in the Dawro Region

Year/Criteria	H. Dume	SER 119	F10B 58	SCR 26	Tatu	DAB 96	SCR 15	Nasir	Remeda	SER 125
2019										
Ground cover	2	2	2	3	3	2	3	3	1	2
Seeds per pod	2	2	3	3	4	1	2	4	1	2
Pods per plant	3	2	2	4	4	2	3	4	1	1
Pod loading	4	4	3	3	3	4	3	3	3	3
Seed size	3	3	3	2	2	1	3	4	2	3
Seed color	3	2	3	4	4	2	3	3	2	2
Grain yield	4	2	4	5	5	3	4	2	2	3
Total score	21	17	20	24	25	15	21	23	12	16
Rank	5	3	6	10	9	2	7	8	1	4

2020										
Ground cover	3	4	3	4	4	2	4	4	3	4
Seeds per pod	3	3	4	4	5	4	3	5	2	3
Pods per plant	4	3	3	5	5	2	4	5	3	2
Pod loading	5	5	4	4	4	5	4	4	5	4
Seed size	4	4	4	3	3	2	4	5	2	4
Seed color	4	2	4	5	5	4	4	4	4	3
Grain yield	5	3	5	6	6	3	5	3	3	3
Total score	28	24	27	31	32	22	28	30	22	23
Rank	6	4	5	9	10	1	6	8	1	3
Over season	49	41	47	55	57	37	49	53	36	39
Over all rank	6	4	5	8	9	2	6	7	1	3

Note: H.dume=Hawassa Dume, F10NB58=F10 B.sel new Bilfa 58 (kello), Scale 1-5 (1= excellent, 2= very good, 3 = good, 4= poor, 5 = very poor)

Farmers commonly select common bean varieties based on their adaptability and suitability for multiple purposes (Fekadu, 2013; Berhanu et al., 2018). This implies that the newly improved varieties, Remeda and SER-119, could be easily introduced and integrated into farming systems, considering various subjective priority criteria. While locally adapted crop varieties may exhibit resilience to changing climates and maintain yields, they often have lower productivity and limited responsiveness to fertilizers compared to improved varieties. With the country's population increasing by 2.6% annually, the adoption of fertilizer-responsive and higher-yielding improved common bean varieties appears economically viable to address the growing population and ensure food security. Additionally, a reported 35% loss in productivity was noted when using local common bean varieties instead of improved ones (Kassa and Merkinch, 2020).

Conclusion

This study showed significant differences in yield and yield-associated traits measured from the tested common bean varieties. Accordingly, the average yield of the varieties was 1312kg/ha. However, Remeda, DAB 96, and SER 119 varieties showed an average yield of 1641, 1601, and 1588.7kg/ha respectively. Similarly, the district farmers preferred these varieties in the first, the second, and the third rank using their preference criteria. Besides, these varieties also out-yielded other varieties comparing them with yield and associated traits measured by the researchers. Hence, these better-yielding and farmers' preferred varieties, Remeda, DAB 96, and SER 119, are recommended for large-scale production in the tested districts and areas with similar agro ecological zones. For the future, released common bean varieties in the separate gene pools, sets are needed to be evaluated to capture variability of genotypes.

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